

Exploring Personal-Organisational Values, Perception of Psychological Climate and Quality of Work Life among Employees

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The research emphasizes on connecting personal values with organizational values (values congruence), affecting job satisfaction and commitment, with cultural differences playing a role. Psychological climate, shaped by leadership, communication, and quality of work life factors, molds employee outcomes. The study aims to explore how personal-organizational values harmony and psychological climate perceptions affect employees' quality of work-life. It seeks to understand their experiences and mechanisms involved, contributing to existing knowledge. This study was qualitative research and was an exploratory study. The sample size was 11 participants from the government and private sectors. The sampling method that was used in the study was purposive sampling. The interviews of these participants were audio-recorded. Data analysis of the transcripts was done using thematic analysis, where global themes came out to be: (1) development and growth; (2) interest in work; (3) positive mental health; (4) leadership; (5) teamwork; (6) changes needed. While the sub themes came out to be: (1) learning; (2) creativity; (3) knowledge; (4) satisfaction; (5) less workload; (6) manageable workload; (7) collaboration; (8) individualistic culture; (9) timing; (10) infrastructure; (11) simplicity; discipline; (12) friendliness; (13) Hierarchy of leadership. The analysis reveals key themes in Indian government and private jobs, including values alignment, psychological climate, and quality of work life. Positive aspects like growth, learning, and job satisfaction are highlighted. Themes like organizational dynamics, leadership, and policy changes proved to be crucial for success.

Keywords: Satisfaction, values, growth, leadership, quality of work life

This study examines personal-organizational values, focusing on the alignment between individuals' personal values and those of their organization, and its influence on employee attitudes and behaviors. The concept is rooted in Cameron and Quinn's (1995) work, *Diagnosing and Changing Organizational Culture: Based on the Competing Values Framework*, which emphasized that value similarity enhances employee satisfaction and organizational effectiveness.

Another key concept is psychological climate, defined as individuals' perceptions of their work environment and its impact on psychological well-being. One of the earliest references is Kurt Lewin's study, *Group Decision and Social Change*, which linked psychological climate to group dynamics and decision-making. The third concept, quality of work life (QWL), refers to employees' overall satisfaction and well-being at work, influenced by factors such as job security, compensation, growth opportunities, and the

work environment. Hackman and Oldham's (1974) study introduced the Job Diagnostic Survey to assess job satisfaction and employee well-being.

The variables of the study are personal-organizational values, psychological climate, and quality of work life. Accordingly, the literature review is organized into three sections addressing each variable.

A substantial body of literature highlights the importance of personal-organizational values alignment, often examined through person-organization fit (PO fit). Kristof-Brown, Zimmerman, and Johnson (2005) found that PO fit is positively related to job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and intention to stay. Chatman and Barsade (1995) emphasized values congruence as a core element of organizational culture influencing employee behavior and performance. Cable and DeRue (2002) reported that higher PO fit reduces turnover intentions, while O'Reilly, Chatman, and Caldwell (1991) found positive relationships between values congruence, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment.

Cross-cultural research by Chen and Francesco (2003) showed that the relationship between PO fit and job satisfaction is stronger in collectivistic cultures. Edwards and Cable (2009) further demonstrated that PO fit is positively associated with employee engagement, particularly when personal values strongly align with organizational values.

Overall, existing literature suggests that alignment between personal and organizational values positively affects employee attitudes and behaviors, including job satisfaction, commitment, and performance. However, research gaps remain, particularly regarding the antecedents and negative consequences of values misalignment, the examination of alignment at group and organizational levels, and variations across sectors and contexts.

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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Review of Literature

Early work on psychological climate by James and Jones (1974) described it as employees' shared perceptions of their work environment and outlined six key dimensions, including innovation, autonomy, and reward orientation. Later researchers expanded this view. Schneider et al. (1998) proposed a four-dimension framework of vision, social support, autonomy, and task orientation and showed that these factors were positively associated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment, while reducing intentions to quit. Similarly, Parker et al. (2003) identified seven dimensions of psychological climate, such as support for innovation, performance orientation, and employee development, all of which were linked to higher job satisfaction, commitment, and performance.

Leadership has been consistently recognized as a major influence on psychological climate. Riggle et al. (2009) found that transformational leadership enhances psychological climate and job satisfaction, whereas abusive supervision has a negative impact. Organizational culture and communication also play a significant role; Agarwal et al. (2012) demonstrated that trust-based cultures and open communication improve psychological climate and employee well-being. Overall, research indicates that psychological climate strongly affects employee attitudes and outcomes, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and performance (James & Jones, 1974). Leadership, culture, and communication are central to shaping these perceptions (Bagga et al., 2023). Despite extensive research, further investigation is needed into how psychological climate develops, how it affects organizational-level outcomes, and which workplace factors most strongly influence positive or negative climates (James & Jones, 1974; Edwards & Cable, 2009).

Quality of work life (QWL) refers to the extent to which employees can fulfill their personal needs and goals through their work and includes elements such as job satisfaction, work-life balance, career growth, and the work environment (Hackman & Oldham, 1974). Walton (1975) proposed an influential model identifying eight dimensions of QWL, including fair compensation, safe working conditions, opportunities for growth, work-life balance, and social relevance of work. Empirical evidence consistently links higher QWL with positive employee outcomes. For instance, Singh and Dixit (2020) found that QWL is positively related to job satisfaction and organizational commitment among Indian IT professionals. Work-life balance has been shown to play a particularly important role in employee well-being and satisfaction (Singh et al., 2022) while career development opportunities (Hultin & Szucs, 2016) and physical work conditions (Gifford et al., 2002) also significantly influence employee attitudes and performance.

Although existing research highlights the importance of QWL, gaps remain. More studies are required to examine employees' subjective perceptions of QWL, its impact on organizational outcomes such as productivity and turnover, and how different workplace conditions and employee characteristics shape QWL experiences.

The conceptual framework of this study is grounded in established theories from organizational behavior and psychology. Social Exchange Theory explains employee behavior as a response to perceived rewards and costs within the organization (Blau, 1964). Conservation of Resources Theory emphasizes the importance of supportive environments in helping employees preserve personal

resources and manage stress (Kim, Park, & Niu, 2017). Self-Determination Theory highlights autonomy, competence, and relatedness as essential psychological needs that drive motivation and satisfaction (Deci et al., 2000). Together, these theories help explain how personal-organizational values alignment and psychological climate influence employees' perceptions of work, ultimately shaping their quality of work life. The framework integrates personal values, organizational values, psychological climate, and QWL to better understand how their interaction affects employee well-being and work outcomes.

Rationale of the Study

The rationale for this qualitative study lies in understanding how exploring and aligning personal and organizational values, along with perceptions of psychological climate, impacts work-life quality. It aims to delve into the experiences of both government and private sector employees amidst continuous exposure to technology, shedding light on how this alignment influences their work life quality. Moreover, by emphasizing the subjective nature of work-life quality and the need for deeper insights, this study seeks to highlight the importance of fostering positive psychological climates and aligning values to create supportive environments for employees.

Furthermore, this research underscores the complementary role of qualitative methods alongside quantitative approaches. While quantitative studies provide statistical evidence, qualitative research offers a nuanced understanding of employees' experiences, contributing to a comprehensive grasp of the topic. By adopting a constructivist approach, this study aims to construct meaning from employees' experiences, providing valuable insights into how aligning personal-organizational values and fostering positive psychological climates can enhance employee well-being, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, ultimately improving the overall quality of work life.

Objective of the Study

The major objective of the current study "Exploring the alignment between personal-organizational values and perceptions of psychological climate on quality of work life" is to understand the experiences and perspectives of employees and how these experiences result in their quality of work life.

Research Questions

The specific objectives of the study are-

- To explore the relationship between personal-organizational values alignment and quality of work life.
- To explore the impact of perceptions of psychological climate on quality of work life.
- To identify the experiences and perspectives of employees regarding the relationship between personal-organizational values alignment and perceptions of psychological climate and quality of work life.
- To understand the mechanisms through which alignment between personal organizational values and perceptions of psychological climate impact quality of work life.
- To provide insights into the importance of aligning personal and organizational values and creating a positive psychological climate for the benefit of employees and organizations.
- To contribute to the existing body of knowledge on the

experiences of personal and organizational values, psychological climate, and quality of work life in organisations.

Method

Participants

The sample size was 11 participants who were both male and female from various parts of India and they were from the government and private sectors. The sampling method that was used in the study was purposive sampling.

Inclusion Criteria

The participants should be Indian citizens. The participants should be between the ages of 22 years to 60 years. The participants should be working in the organization for at least 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria

The participants should not be a part time job employee. The participants should not be psychologically unfit. The participant should not be a businessman.

Measures

The collection of data for this present study was done by a semi-interview method. The interviews were done in a semi-structured manner allowing room for the free flow of conversation while still keeping an interview schedule which helped to guide the interview. The research interview schedule was validated by three professors in the same field. There were also changes suggested by these experts which were positively incorporated.

Few questions from the final interview schedule are-

- Describe your opinions of the psychological environment within the organization?
- What are the changes or improvements you would like to see within your organization where the aspects like quality of work life and personal-organizational values are taken care of?
- What are the coping strategies you use to face the challenges arising from a negative psychological climate?

Procedure

The researcher informed the participant about the details of the study and how it would help increase the knowledge base. They were also informed about their right to terminate whenever they wished to. They were then presented with the consent form and asked to fill it via Google Form if they agreed to participate in the interview. Once they filled out the consent form, the recording began. A few general questions were asked to build rapport to make the participant more comfortable. They were also asked the demographic questions and then the interview proceeded according to the interview schedule.

Ethical Considerations

There were a few ethical considerations that were kept in mind and adhered to while the study was being conducted. First, the details of the participant were kept confidential and only shared with the supervisor.

Second, the participants were allowed to withdraw the study whenever they wanted to. This also included the non-usage of any of their information. The participants were told in advance about this and also about how their participation was completely voluntary. They were asked for their informed consent in order to have evidence of their voluntary participation if they did so.

Third, the well-being of the participants was the utmost priority of the researcher. In case of any issue arising while in data collection, the whole process was terminated and the participant was made to feel better. The researcher also did not ask questions that could trigger the participant without prior approval.

Fourth, there was a debriefing that was conducted after the study was over wherein the participants were allowed to answer questions and they were also told about how the data would be used.

Lastly, the study received full ethical approval from the IRB ethics committee. All interviews were recorded with the permission of participants and they were later anonymized and transcribed. Anonymized interviews were stored on a password-protected computer for later analysis.

Results

Data Analysis

Data was collected from participants through a semi-structured interview. In order to do data analysis, thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) was used in this qualitative study.

The data analysis reveals several key themes related to government and private jobs in India. These themes include the importance of personal and organizational values alignment, the significance of psychological climate, and the concept of quality of work life. The study also highlights the positive aspects of government and private jobs, including opportunities for development and growth, a focus on learning and creativity, job satisfaction, and positive mental health. Workload management, teamwork dynamics, leadership styles, simplicity, discipline, friendliness, and the hierarchy of leadership all play essential roles in the organizational context. Additionally, the findings emphasize the need for policy and rule changes, consideration of working hours, infrastructure, knowledge and skills, and adapting to evolving conditions to ensure the effectiveness and success of government organizations in India.

The major themes of the data analysis are as follows-

Development and Growth

Government jobs also offer prospects for progress and growth. Participants shared their experiences with learning new skills and taking on additional responsibilities, which can lead to promotions and increased pay.

Learning

Various government organisations and agencies organise innovation challenges in order to engage the tech community and encourage it to propose solutions to public-sector problems. As responded by a participant, “...too many areas are there where you can enhance yourself by learning.”

Creativity

Learning and development in the Indian government sector is vital to guaranteeing the efficiency and effectiveness of public services. There is a focus on creating a more agile and knowledgeable workforce to meet the evolving needs of the employees and the country. As per the respondent's response “it has a great creativity and I use means that I can engage myself in learning these technical technologies, new technologies which are coming. So, I don't feel any boredom in that.”

Interest for Work

Government jobs in India are found to be interesting and attractive to many individuals for several reasons like job security, attractive pay and benefits, work-life balance, social status, job diversity, opportunities for advancement, job benefits for the family, job stability, pension and retirement benefits, scope for social impact, training and learning opportunities, perks and allowances etc.

Knowledge

Government departments frequently engage in staff training and development, offering opportunity to improve skills and expertise which enhances their knowledge. As per a respondent's response, "*I can engage myself in learning these technical technologies, new technologies which are coming*".

Satisfaction

Government jobs in India are often considered satisfying for various reasons like job security, steady income, pension and retirement benefits, work life balance, social status and prestige, career progression, variety of roles, contribution to society, stable work environment etc. As per a respondent's response, "*they are organising meetups, they organise the seminars with the senior most advocates and the CGI of the High Court and Supreme Court, who get the motivation towards giving up the society and who get the things real, real things out from the world, keeping us in the real world, not in a reel world*". The participants are also happy because of the job satisfaction. This can be observed when one of the participant quoted the following, "*I am fully satisfied because it says it comes under science and technology and one is promoted after giving a review so when you salary get high hike and then it gives a satisfaction that if you are working for the organization then your organization is also working for you*".

Positive Mental Health

Government jobs in India can contribute to positive mental health in several ways. Positive mental health ensures less and manageable workload. It keeps life in the work place stable. As per a respondent's response, "*...it keeps me busy. And I have no problem with it. Like, it doesn't affect anything because it's giving a certain amount which is more than sufficient to live a good life. So it's not affecting anything. It's in only good for giving lots of amount and PF. So after you get retired, you get the sufficient amount so that you can live the rest of your life*".

Less Work Load

For a variety of reasons, government positions in India are sometimes perceived as having a lesser burden than those in the private sector. Fixed working hours, increased job security, restricted responsibility, bureaucratic processes that inhibit decision-making, less technical demands, promotion based on seniority rather than performance, and a less competitive climate for employment retention and promotions are some of these benefits. However, it is critical to recognise that workload varies greatly depending on the department and post, and workload assessments are subjective and may not always correctly represent the real demands of government occupations. As per a respondent's response, "*Sometime there comes any work means time bounded work so that sometimes give means work due to work pressure. This gives a pressure and otherwise its OK No problem*".

Manageable Workload

Structured working hours, regular holidays, a growing emphasis on work-life balance, efficient time management, supportive work cultures, technology and automation adoption, employee welfare programmes, and adherence to labour laws and regulations all contribute to a manageable workload in Indian offices. These characteristics, taken together, lead to a work climate in which people may effectively balance their professional and personal life. Workload can vary based on the business and job, and some people may have larger workloads during peak seasons or in high-demand industries. As per a respondent's response, "*Whenever I need any holiday my organisation used to give if I have not too many questions are asked that why and where you are going, so that means every employees should know where the cruciality*".

Team Work

Teamwork in India's governmental and private sectors has both similarities and distinctions. Teamwork in the government sector is frequently organised in a hierarchical framework, with a focus on conforming to established rules and laws. Long tenures and inter-departmental collaboration are common, and the emphasis is on meeting specified public service goals. Private sector cooperation, on the other hand, is distinguished by agility, goal-oriented methods, innovation, and cross-functional collaboration to achieve corporate objectives. In the private sector, performance-based incentives and competitive conditions are more widespread. However, due to factors such as organisational culture, industry, and leadership style, differences in collaboration dynamics can occur within each sector, emphasising the significance of good communication and shared commitment to accomplishing common goals in both government and private sector contexts.

Collaboration

Collaboration is essential in government sector teamwork in India because it promotes efficient and effective delivery of public services, resolution of difficult issues, and responsible resource management. It also promotes openness, public participation, and the creation of a trained and adaptive government staff. As per a respondent's response, "*Team work is very essential part in my organization because one means with the team work only with teamwork can one execute things very effectively. So I do work in team work and communicate with others*".

As per one respondent, the team work in the organization is not good because they are collaborating with other countries where the timings do not match so communication is also minimal. As per his response, "*sometimes difficult to work with them difficult to explain about my thing, because like, we need to manage only a single call to discuss what we're working on. But yeah, we, I mean, if it's a bit difficult to, like, manage, I mean, it's difficult to understand. And also, like, when I joined, you know, the people who's working from other countries, sometimes it's difficult to understand their client*".

Individualistic Culture

There are a few organizations where there is hardly any team work. They believe in working independently and then collaborating and helping in the end. As per a respondent's response, "*We do not like we do not team up and do things. We do our work individually. But in the end, we have to like, gather and do the work and help each other*".

Changes Needed

Policy and rule changes are required for an organisation to adapt to changing conditions, increase efficiency, and remain aligned with its aims and values. Organisations operate in dynamic contexts, and when new issues and opportunities emerge, policies and procedures must be revised to properly handle them. Changes can also accommodate technological improvements, fluctuations in market patterns, and changing legal and regulatory constraints. Furthermore, changing policies and procedures may encourage creativity, increase employee happiness, and develop a culture of continual improvement. Organisations may maintain their relevance, agility, and capacity to manage a quickly changing business landscape by evaluating and amending these rules on a regular basis.

Timings

Working hours are critical in organisations because they provide a structure for staff productivity and operational effectiveness. Consistent and well-defined working hours assist employees build a predictable pattern, which aids in job planning and time management. They allow teams to coordinate their efforts, arrange meetings, and guarantee that key tasks are accomplished during normal business hours. Furthermore, sticking to set work schedules fosters work-life balance, decreases burnout, and promotes employee well-being, eventually improving job satisfaction and retention. As per a respondent's response, *"the thing is that timing thing they should fix the timing. It's very bad for government employees like they cannot give time to the family or their children."*

Infrastructure

Infrastructure plays an important role in any organization. If the infrastructure of any organization is good then it keeps the motivation to work alive. A well-planned and employee centric infrastructure not only improves physical comfort and efficiency, but it also promotes a good work culture, nurtures employee well-being, and fits with their values. In turn, this can increase motivation and overall job satisfaction, resulting in a more engaged and productive staff. As per a respondent's response, *"one should have his own setup at the user department of mobile"*. As per another respondent's response, *"there is no cleanliness. So they should clean the youknow, like infrastructure."*

Knowledge and Skills

Knowledge and skills should be prioritized. There are a few organizations where number of years of work matter to people but skills and knowledge do not which should be an important element. Prioritising knowledge and skills across the number of working years is essential for organisational performance in the modern workplace. While experience is important, it is the relevance and applicability of an employee's knowledge and abilities that drives creativity, problem-solving, and adaptation. Continuous learning and development emphasises the ability of organisations to leverage the newest skills while keeping up with quickly changing sectors and technology. Focusing on knowledge and skills also encourages diversity and inclusion by recognising and appreciating the contributions of people from varied backgrounds who may offer new views and capabilities to the organisation. Finally, in today's changing corporate world, a knowledge and skills-centered strategy helps organisations to stay competitive, adaptable, and future-ready.

As per a respondent's response, *"shall be appointed on the basis of the knowledge or research skills he really has or holds not on the basis of how much of your practice he really holds. They are people who I know who hold practice for four to five years, but they don't have any knowledge"*.

Leadership

Leadership style plays an important role in organisations because it has a direct influence on staff motivation, job satisfaction, and overall performance. Employees respond differently to different leadership styles, which range from authoritarian to democratic, transformative to transactional. Employees are inspired and engaged by effective leadership styles, which establish a pleasant work atmosphere and encourage creativity and innovation. Servant leadership and coaching leadership styles place an emphasis on employee growth and well-being, which increases work satisfaction and trust. Overly dictatorial leadership styles, on the other side, may harm staff morale and productivity. Finally, leadership style is a significant aspect in an organization's success since it shapes organisational culture and influences employee attitudes and behaviours. As per a respondent's response, *"he (the HR) always motivates me to work and like there are times like, where we do not agree with each other ideas like we but we but we are open to discuss."*

Simplicity

Simplicity in leadership style is achieved through clear and straightforward communication, transparent information sharing, and streamlined decision-making processes. Simplicity is prioritised by focusing on important goals, avoiding superfluous bureaucracy, and assigning duties based on team members' skills. They actively listen to criticism, act simply, and encourage team members to take responsibility of their job. Embracing simplicity and consistency, as well as a dedication to openness and accessibility, fosters a climate in which trust, clarity, and effectiveness flourish, eventually contributing to the organization's success. As per a respondent's response who himself shows leadership in his organization says, *"Lower service staff I used to check out. I do draw the things in pen and paper so that once I listed my work done or the work which I have to get from my lowers, I used to write everything on pen and paper. So communication means that way. I think that my communication with others is very nice."*

Discipline

Leaders can teach employees discipline in organizations through their own exemplary behavior and effective leadership practices. Leaders that constantly display timeliness, commitment to deadlines, and a strong work ethic urge their colleagues to do the same. Setting clear standards and keeping people accountable for their obligations, as well as offering constructive comments and acknowledging disciplined behaviour, encourages discipline. Effective communication from leaders ensures that employees understand the value of discipline and how it contributes to the success of the organisation. Furthermore, leaders may create and maintain a disciplined work culture by supporting consistency, fairness, and a focus on long-term goals, so establishing an atmosphere in which workers respect and practise discipline in their everyday work. As per a respondent's response, *"...there are no barricades or barriers to you can't directly approach but you need to, firstly proper follow the proper channels."*

Friendliness

Organisational leaders may establish a pleasant connection with their employees by displaying approachability, empathy, and genuine concern for their well-being. They should actively listen to employees' issues, offer assistance, and implement an open-door policy that promotes open communication. Being accessible to provide assistance and mentorship while also recognising and applauding employees' accomplishments contributes to the development of trust and camaraderie. Leaders may have casual interactions with workers and show interest in their personal and professional development, which can contribute to a healthy and welcoming work atmosphere. Leaders must find a balance between being approachable and asserting their authority, ensuring that the pleasant connection does not compromise their leadership responsibilities or generate problems within the team. As per a respondent's response, *"They are very friendly so we do not have any problem, and the responsibility rules and regulation, and the leadership, which controls all of this, the leader control. So things they are very light and polite."*

Hierarchy of Leadership

Organisations benefit from a hierarchy of leadership because it gives structure, clarity, and a well-defined line of command. It guarantees that an established hierarchy of authority and responsibility exists, which may help to speed decision-making processes, promote accountability, and allow effective communication and coordination within the organisation. Hierarchy facilitates task and responsibility delegation, allowing leaders to focus on strategic planning and high-level decision-making while delegating operational chores to lower levels. It also creates a framework for career promotion and professional development, which encourages individuals to seek for success within the organisation. As per a respondent's response, *"I report to my manager and my manager reports to the assistant vice president. So that's how it usually goes."* However, organisations must find a balance to ensure that hierarchy does not suffocate innovation, free communication, or the organization's capacity to adapt to changing circumstances.

In conclusion, the results reveal several key themes related to government and private jobs in India. These themes include the importance of personal and organizational values alignment, the significance of psychological climate, and the concept of quality of work life. The study also highlights the positive aspects of government and private jobs, including opportunities for development and growth, a focus on learning and creativity, job satisfaction, and positive mental health. Workload management, teamwork dynamics, leadership styles, simplicity, discipline, friendliness, and the hierarchy of leadership all play essential roles in the organizational context. Additionally, the findings emphasize the need for policy and rule changes, consideration of working hours, infrastructure, knowledge and skills, and adapting to evolving conditions to ensure the effectiveness and success of government organizations in India.

Discussion

The data analysis conducted in this qualitative study offers valuable insights into the realm of government employment in India. Key findings revolve around various themes, shedding light on the working conditions, employee sentiments, and organizational

dynamics within the public sector and private sector. Research by Srivastava and Sharma (2019) explored career development practices in Indian organizations, including both government and private sectors. Their findings support the qualitative study's observation of ample opportunities for development and career growth, emphasizing the importance of continuous learning and skill enhancement in both sectors. Noteworthy findings include the ample opportunities for development and career growth within government roles and private organizations as well, emphasizing the importance of continuous learning and skills enhancement. A study by Singh and Verma (2020) investigated the role of innovation in Indian organizations, highlighting the significance of fostering a culture of innovation and creativity to meet the evolving demands of the private sector. This aligns with the qualitative study's emphasis on the importance of innovation in both government and private service. Participants also underlined the significance of fostering a culture of innovation and creativity to meet the evolving demands of private service. Job satisfaction in government roles is attributed to factors such as job security, competitive compensation, work-life balance, and diverse career opportunities. The study highlights the necessity of prioritizing knowledge and skills, emphasizing their importance over years of experience. Furthermore, both government and private jobs are found to promote positive mental health through manageable workloads and job stability. Effective teamwork and collaboration are recognized as essential components of both the public and private sectors. Organizations should remain adaptable through policy and rule changes to foster a culture of improvement. Leadership styles that promote simplicity, discipline, and friendliness can enhance the work atmosphere, while a well-defined hierarchy of leadership is essential for streamlined decision-making and accountability. A study by Mishra et al. (2020) investigated the impact of leadership styles on organizational culture in Indian government institutions. Their findings suggest that leadership styles emphasizing simplicity, discipline, and friendliness contribute to a positive work atmosphere, supporting the qualitative study's recommendations for effective leadership styles. Research conducted by Gupta et al. (2018) examined factors influencing job satisfaction among government employees in India. Their study identified job security, competitive compensation, work-life balance, and diverse career opportunities as key factors contributing to job satisfaction, consistent with the findings of the qualitative study. Another study by Kumar and Kumar (2019) investigated the impact of job characteristics on mental health among employees in Indian organizations. Their findings suggest that manageable workloads and job stability promote positive mental health outcomes, supporting the qualitative study's observation regarding the positive effects of both government and private jobs on mental health. Research by Verma and Chauhan (2017) examined the role of teamwork and collaboration in organizational effectiveness in the Indian context. Their study highlighted the importance of effective teamwork and collaboration in both public and private sectors, corroborating the qualitative study's findings on the essential components of organizational dynamics.

These findings have far-reaching implications for human resource management, organizational culture, and leadership in government and institutions, ultimately contributing to enhanced job satisfaction, improved performance, and better outcomes in the public and private sector.

Limitations of the Study

The study's findings may be limited by its small sample of 11 participants, which reduces the ability to generalize results. Including a larger and more varied group would strengthen the external validity and support broader conclusions about the links between personal-organizational values, psychological climate, and quality of work life. Using purposive sampling could also introduce bias, as participants may share similar viewpoints, potentially excluding a wider range of experiences in government and private sectors. Nonetheless, the study offers important insights into these factors within the Indian context.

Conclusion

The study of government employment in India offers valuable insights into workplace conditions, employee perspectives, and organizational processes. It highlights opportunities for career growth and emphasizes the importance of ongoing learning. Job satisfaction in public roles is linked to job security, fair compensation, and work-life balance. The research also stresses supporting innovation, mental well-being, and skill development. Collaborative teamwork, adaptable policies, and straightforward leadership styles contribute to a positive organizational culture. These findings provide guidance for HR practices, leadership, and culture to improve employee satisfaction and outcomes in both public and private sectors.

Implications of the Study

The study provides guidance for organizational practices, employee well-being, and HR management. In IT and other sectors, aligning personal and organizational values and fostering a positive psychological climate can enhance employee environments. Proactive measures addressing job satisfaction and work-life balance can be implemented based on values alignment and climate. HR strategies should focus on job security, competitive compensation, and development opportunities. Policy changes in government organizations, including working hours and infrastructure, are also recommended. Leadership development, efficient workload management, continuous learning, cultural innovation, adaptability, and mental health promotion are emphasized to improve work environments. Overall, the study offers practical insights for enhancing quality of work life across sectors.

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Received January 13, 2025

Revision received January 26, 2025

Accepted January 29, 2025